

A NOTE ON THE FRIEDEL AND CRAFT'S CONDENSATION OF ACETYL CHLORIDE WITH DICHLOROBENZENES

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Dichlorobenzenes have been successfully condensed with acetyl chloride to obtain dichloroacetophenones. The products have been characterised by the usual derivatives and oxidised to dichlorobenzoic acids

Dichloroacetophenones were required in this laboratory in connection with work on substituted chalcones and acridines. The easiest method of obtaining these would be by the Friedel and Craft's condensation of acetyl chloride with dichlorobenzenes. Previous attempts by various workers in this direction have been unsuccessful. Thus Boeskin (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1908, 27, 10) found that the condensation of acetyl chloride with *o*-, *m*- and *p*-dichlorobenzenes gave 2%, 0.4% and nil yields of the corresponding acetophenones. He attributed this failure to the self-condensation of acetyl chloride (Combes reaction). Benzoyl chloride, which does not undergo self-condensation, on the other hand, gave with *o*- and *m*-dichlorobenzenes 80 to 90% of dichlorobenzophenones. *p*-Dichlorobenzene, however, gave only a tarry product. Roberts and Turner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1832) condensed acetyl chloride with *o*-dichlorobenzene and obtained 40% yield of 3 : 4-dichloroacetophenone. We have now reinvestigated the condensation of acetyl chloride with dichlorobenzenes with the following results.

Good yields of dichloroacetophenones from the three isomeric dichlorobenzenes can be obtained if the condensations are carried without any solvent and with an excess of acetyl chloride and aluminium chloride. The best conditions for obtaining the maximum yields are one part of dichlorobenzene, one part of acetyl chloride and two parts of anhydrous aluminium chloride, heated together on a water-bath for 5 hours. Under these conditions *o*-dichlorobenzene gives 90% yield (the yields in all cases have been calculated on the quantity of dichlorobenzene used in the experiments without making allowance for the recovered dichlorobenzene) of 3 : 4-dichloroacetophenone, m. p. 75°; Roberts and Turner (*loc. cit.*) record the m. p. 76°. It has been characterised by formation of an oxime, semicarbazone, phenylhydrazone and 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

m-Dichlorobenzene under the condition gives 70% yield of 2 : 4-dichloroacetophenone (b. p. 235-240° at ordinary pressure). It solidifies later, m. p. 42°. It gives an oxime, semicarbazone, and 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. On oxidation with either alkaline potassium permanganate or sodium hypobromite a quantitative yield of 2 : 4-dichlorobenzoic acid (m.p. 164°) is obtained.

p-Dichlorobenzene gives 50% yield of 2 : 5-dichloroacetophenone b. p. 245-250°, characterised by an oxime, semicarbazone and 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. On oxidation it gives 2 : 5-dichlorobenzoic acid, m. p. 152°.

The good yields in the condensation of acetyl chloride with dichlorobenzenes and the quantitative oxidation of the resulting dichloroacetophenones to the corresponding dichlorobenzoic acids can, hence, be used to prepare the dichlorobenzoic acids which are otherwise difficult to obtain.

With a view to finding the best conditions a number of experiments were made with *o*-dichlorobenzene, the reactants being heated together on a water-bath for 5 hours. Ice and hydrochloric acid were added and steam distilled. The product recovered by ether extraction was purified by fractionation. The results are shown in the following table.

TABLE I

<i>o</i> -Dichloro- benzene:	Acetyl chloride.	Solvent.	AlCl ₃ .	Yield of dichloro- acetophenone.
10 g.	10 g.	CS ₂ (40 v. c.)	30 g.	15%
10	10	No solvent.	40	90
10	10	" "	20	90
10	10	" "	10	20
10	5	" "	20	8

Adam and Noller's modification, namely the use of acetic anhydride in place of acetyl chloride (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1889) was not satisfactory as the yield was about 20% only. 3 : 4-Dichloroacetophenone formed an *oxime*, as glistening needles from alcohol, m. p. 110°. (Found : Cl, 34.6. C₈H₇ONCl₂ requires Cl, 34.8 per cent). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 250°. (Found : Cl, 29.2. C₉H₉ON₃Cl₂ requires Cl, 28.9 per cent). The *phenylhydrazone* crystallised in pale yellow shining plates, m. p. 122-24°. (Found : Cl, 25.9. C₁₄H₁₂N₂Cl₂ requires Cl 25.5 per cent)

2 : 4-Dichloroacetophenone had b. p. 235-240°. $D_4^{25} = 1.322$; $n_D^{25} = 1.5606$. It solidified later and had m. p. 42°. (Found : Cl, 37.8. C₈H₆OCl₂ requires Cl, 37.6 per cent). It gave an *oxime* as prismatic needles from alcohol, m. p. 152°. (Found : Cl, 34.9. C₈H₇ONCl₂ requires Cl, 34.8 per cent). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 208°. (Found : Cl, 28.8. C₉H₉ON₃Cl₂ requires Cl, 28.9 per cent). On oxidation it gave 2 : 4-dichlorobenzoic acid, m. p. 164°.

2 : 5-Dichloroacetophenone had b. p. 245-250° at ordinary pressure. It had $D_4^{25} = 1.352$; $n_D^{25} = 1.5595$ (Found : Cl, 38.1. C₈H₆OCl₂ requires Cl, 37.6 per cent). It formed an *oxime* as long, thin, woolly needles, m. p. 127°. (Found : Cl, 34.3. C₈H₇ONCl₂ requires Cl, 34.8 per cent). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 202-203°. (Found : Cl, 29.3. C₉H₉ON₃Cl₂ requires Cl, 28.9 per cent). On oxidation it gave 2 : 5-dichlorobenzoic acid, m. p. 152°.